

PROJECT DELIVERABLE REPORT

Greening the economy in line with
the sustainable development goals

D7.3.1 NAIADES Front-End and HMI Mechanisms and Integrated Decision Support Engine – User manual for Alicante

A holistic water ecosystem for digitisation of urban water sector
SC5-11-2018

Digital solutions for water: linking the physical and digital world for water solutions

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Abbreviations

ACF	Autocorrelation Function
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
API	Application Programming Interface
DSS	Decision Support System
GBM	Gradient Boosting Machine
GUI	Graphical User Interface
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KDE	Kernel Density Estimate
KNN	K-Nearest Neighbor
LSTM	Long-Short Term Memory
MAPE	Mean Absolute Percentage Error
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NN	Neural Network
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
RF	Random Forest
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
RNN	Recurrent Neural Networks
SVM	Support Vector Machine

1. Summary

This report provides the user manual for UC Alicante, in order to be translated to Spanish for the convenience of the end-users, as well as the smooth adaptation of HMI to the Use Case.

The initial report was delivered in English and it was based on D7.3 HMI and integrated Decision Support System.

The final report was translated in Spanish by the UC leaders, in order to be delivered to the end-users.

2. Introduction

The scope of this deliverable is to provide an overall user manual about HMI, DSS and the other NAIADES components. This document will help the end-users to “unlock” the privileges of using the final platform in testing environments, such as the Use Cases.

D7.3 can be also used for the KPIs evaluation, as it will sustain an important pillar of learning for the end-users, and an actual proof of concept for the Project and its results.

2.1. Navigation into the Alicante UC

2.1.1. Users and Roles

In Alicante Use Case, there is one User created with one overall role. This user has an administrator role, meaning that he/she can see all the UC Alicante Screens.

In order to log in, the end-user has to go to <http://167.71.44.124:2030/auth> and click on the “Connect to Keyrock” button.

*The above IP address will change when the HMI will be deployed in the final NAIADES server.

Figure 2.1-1 Connect to Keyrock

When the end-user clicks on the above button, then he/she is redirected to Keyrock main page.

Figure 2.1-2 Keyrock Sign In

The current user has the email address of alicante-administrator@test.com, which was provided by KT for testing purposes. In future and when UC partners define other roles, new users will be created.

* The credentials will be not shared in this document, due to security measures.

Then, the end-user can click on the “Sign In” button and navigate into HMI’s Home Page.

2.1.2. Language Selection

The end-user clicks on the [drop-down](#) on the top-right menu. He can leave the predefined language, which is English as it is shown in the figure bellow. Or he/she can select Spanish,

Figure. Spanish for Alicante

After this, the end-user can navigate to the HMI to the language of his convenience.

2.1.3. Water Demand

In Alicante’s Water demand screen, HMI provides the UI the water prediction in Alicante. More specifically, it provides:

- Measures from high and low consumption sensors and alerts when a measure surpasses a threshold as well as a map which indicates the sensors’ location.
- Next day water consumption prediction (upper, Average and Lower Forecast)

- Water Consumption with indicator: Attention, Observed, Predicted, Confidence intervals as well as the estimated monthly and yearly consumption
- Next week water consumption prediction (Upper, Average, Lower Forecast)
- Next month water consumption prediction (Upper, Average, Lower Forecast)

Figure 2.1-3 Alicante's Water Demand screen

Functionality 1 - Usage Level Alerts

This functionality is provided by the DSS and HMI. More specifically, HMI provides a map with all the integrated sensors' locations.

Figure 2.1-4 Alicante Map & DSS Usage Level Alerts

DSS defines a water leakage by analyzing the short-term prediction for the water consumption with the actual water consumption. If the real consumption is higher than the forecast, higher than e.g 5%, then there is probably a leak or an abnormal situation on the area. If there is a lower consumption, then DSS provides an alert demonstrating the forecast values and the actual values, as well as the area where this leak was detected (e.g., Benaluá).

This functionality can be shown by clicking on the alert button. Then, a pop-up is shown for the Leakage Detection and the Consumption Levels, as it is shown below.

Alerts

x

Leakage Detection

16/11/2022 04:00

● No leakages detected in area: Alipark

16/11/2022 04:00

● No leakages detected in area: Autobuses

16/11/2022 04:00

● No leakages detected in area: Rambla

16/11/2022 04:00

● Possible Leakage Detected in area: Benalua

16/11/2022 04:00

● No leakages detected in area: Mercado

16/11/2022 04:00

● No leakages detected in area: Montaneta

Consumption Levels

16/11/2022 04:00

● Low Consumption to: Alipark

16/11/2022 04:00

● Low Consumption to: Autobuses

16/11/2022 04:00

● High Consumption to: Rambla

16/11/2022 04:00

● Low Consumption to: Benalua

16/11/2022 04:00

● Low Consumption to: Mercado

16/11/2022 04:00

● Low Consumption to: Montaneta

Figure 2.1-5 DSS Alerts for Leakage Detection and Consumption Levels

As it is shown on the pop-up above, there is the alert and the time detected, as well as a red pin (if the alert is crucial) or a green pin (if there is no actual alert - normal state). The map interacts with these pins, as they are integrated on it, every time there is a DSS alert or notification.

Functionality 2, 3, 4 - Daily, Next Hours and Week Forecast

First, HMI provides a graph with the daily water consumption on the 7 areas of Alicante, as it is shown below.

Figure 2.1-6 Daily Water Consumption in Alicante Areas

The short-term water prediction provides the hourly, daily and the weekly water consumption prediction in Alicante area. The following graphs are instance of HMI’s adaptation of partners work.

Figure 2.1-7 Next Day and Week Forecast

In the **next hours forecast**, the end-user can see prediction on the water consumption in 7 different areas of Alicante, Alipark, Rambla, Autobuses, Montaneta sectors, Mercado, Benalua, Diputacion. These predictions are set from the next 1 hour until the end of the day.

Moreover, the end-user can click in the right drop-down menu and select the total option, in order to see the overall sum of the 7 areas, as it is shown in the figure below.

Figure 2.1-8 Total Sum of Water Consumption in 7 Areas //Next Hours

In the **next week forecast**, the end-user can see predictions of water consumption in the 7 seven different areas.

Figure 2.1-9 Next Week Forecast

Moreover, there is also the capability of seeing the total sum of all the 7 areas for the next week, as it is shown below.

Figure 2.1-10 Total Sum of Water Consumption in 7 Areas //Next Week

Functionality 4 - Water Demand Prediction (Long-Term)

Deep learning techniques are used for the prediction of monthly and yearly water consumption. This is the long-term water demand model, where it provides intervals (quantities) indicating the maximum and the minimum value of the water consumption for each month rather than a single prediction for each month. In addition, this component provides the monthly and yearly water consumption of each area, as the figure below demonstrates.

Figure 2.1-11 Yearly Water Consumption Prediction from long-term Water Demand Model

The end-user can click in on the drop-down menu, in order to see the rest areas and their expected water consumption in a long-term basis (monthly or yearly). In addition, graphs are provided for each area illustrating the yearly behaviour of the water consumption levels for each area.

With this approach, the end-user can be updated and informed for the Monthly and the Yearly Water Demand and as a result, decrease the water consumption in the Alicante area.

2.1.4. Weather Prediction

In the weather prediction screen, HMI provides a UI of weather prediction in Alicante. More precisely, it provides:

- The current weather in Alicante (Current Temperature, Humidity, Wind Speed and an overall.)
- DSS prediction of the weather per five hours for the following three days (e.g., Possible rain, clear weather, etc.)
- Predictions of the values for Temperature, Humidity and Wind Speed per 6 hours for the following three days
- Weather Historical data
- Weather Historical Graph

As a result, the end-user is enhanced with situation awareness, in order to take action if needed, mainly for the water consumption.

Figure 2.1-12 Alicante's Weather Prediction screen

Figure 2.1-13 Weather Historical Data & Historical Graph

Functionality 1 - Alicante Weather

Here, the end-user can detect the exact temperature, the humidity percentage and the wind speed of the Alicante area.

Figure 2.1-14 Alicante Weather

Functionality 2 - DSS Weather Prediction

Here, the end-user can see prediction on the weather for the next 3 days.

Sistema de ayuda a la toma de decisiones en la predicción del tiempo

05/06/2022 23.4 °C - 26.1 °C

12:00 - 17:00

Clear weather

18:00 - 23:00

Clear weather

06/06/2022 21.5 °C - 26.6 °C

00:00 - 05:00

Possible rain

06:00 - 11:00

Clear weather

12:00 - 17:00

Clear weather

18:00 - 23:00

Possible rain

Figure 2.1-15 DSS Weather Prediction

These predictions/alerts are varied into “Possible rain”, “Clear weather”, “Warm Weather”, “Possible light rain” and “Dry Weather”.

Functionality 3 - Weather Forecast

The weather forecast provides to the end-user, details on the temperature, humidity and wind speed for the next 3 days.

Pronóstico meteorológico												
Día/hora (Local)	05/06/2022 (10:00)	+6h (16:00)	+12h (22:00)	06/06/2022 (04:00)	+24h (10:00)	+30h (16:00)	+36h (22:00)	07/06/2022 (04:00)	+48h (10:00)	+54h (16:00)	+60h (22:00)	08/06/2022 (04:00)
Temperatura	26.1 °C	23.4 °C	21.5 °C	25.1 °C	26.6 °C	23.1 °C	20.5 °C	24.1 °C	26.7 °C	23.2 °C	20.1 °C	26.1 °C
Humedad	64.2 %	73.5 %	83.8 %	71.0 %	65.2 %	77.6 %	81.7 %	62.3 %	58.9 %	71.9 %	77.3 %	39.9 %
Velocidad del viento	2.7km/h	1.0km/h	1.1km/h	2.0km/h	3.1km/h	1.6km/h	1.6km/h	1.9km/h	2.8km/h	1.4km/h	1.6km/h	1.2km/h

Figure 2.1-16 Weather Forecast

The end-user obtains a more complete picture on the upcoming weather and he/she can be prepared in case of unwanted difficulties.

Functionality 4 - Weather Historical data & Graph

The Weather historical table is filled with data from the past 3 days, as it is shown in the following figure.

Historial meteorológico												
Día/hora (Local)	02/06/2022 (10:00)	+6h (16:00)	+12h (22:00)	03/06/2022 (04:00)	+24h (10:00)	+30h (16:00)	+36h (22:00)	04/06/2022 (04:00)	+48h (10:00)	+54h (16:00)	+60h (22:00)	05/06/2022 (04:00)
Temperatura	25.8 °C	24.4 °C	22 °C	21.3 °C	26.6 °C	25.5 °C	21.5 °C	18.1 °C	25.4 °C	27.5 °C	21.8 °C	19 °C
Humedad	62 %	69 %	83 %	87 %	61 %	69 %	84 %	70 %	64 %	45 %	76 %	80 %
Velocidad del viento	2 km/h	1.8 km/h	3.4 km/h	1.3 km/h	3.2 km/h	2.5 km/h	1.1 km/h	0.9 km/h	3.2 km/h	2 km/h	0.7 km/h	0.6 km/h

Figure 2.1-17 Weather Historical Data

These data are used in the historical graph, where the temperature, humidity and the wind speed can be shown from a popup if the end-user hovers on one of the 3 colored lines of the graph.

Figure 2.1-18 Weather Historical Graph

The green line refers to historical humidity, the blue to wind-speed and the red one to temperature.

2.1.5. Salinity Intrusion

In the Salinity Intrusion screen in Alicante, HMI provide awareness on:

- Anomaly Detection graphs on conductivity and flow levels
- DSS alerts
- Interactive Map

Figure 2.1-19 Salinity Intrusion Screen

Functionality 1 - Anomaly Detection graphs on conductivity and flow levels

HMI consumes incoming data from JSI's anomaly meta-signal, as long as the water flow levels, in order to form 2 graphs.

Figure 2.1-20 Anomaly Detection Conductivity & Flow Level

A drop-down is provided on each graph, in order to select the required sensor. Moreover, there is a description of the area for each installed sensor, on the bottom of the graph. Another feature from HMI is that the graphs are scalable, in order to visualize the differences of the incoming measurements and highlight with this way, the conductivity and flow levels.

X axis has the incoming results of anomaly, as long as the Y axis has the time of the selected day. The same approach applies on the Water flow levels graphs.

Functionality 2 - DSS alerts

The DSS alerts generate warnings for infiltration on a specific area where a sensor is installed.

The first thing to do, in order to create the above graphs, is the correlation of the anomalies with the conductivity. In this case, when an anomaly signal is consumed, DSS identifies if the anomaly is related to **high** or **low** conductivity. Then, if there is an anomaly related to high conductivity, a comparison is made on the daily flow with the mean flow of the previous days. If the values of the current day (at a specific time of the day) are larger than the mean daily flow, DSS raises a warning that infiltration has probably caused a conductivity anomaly.

On the other hand, if an anomaly related to low conductivity is received, and there is no rain at the same time, DSS raises a warning that probably something strange is happening, due to low conductivity without rain.

DSS Feed

Probably an infiltration occurred to the area with ID 2;
the alert was triggered from the data coming from the sensors EA003-36 and EA007-36.

Figure 2.1-21 DSS Feed in Salinity Intrusion

In order to achieve this, DSS consumes the anomaly detection alerts, for instance created from EA003-36 sensor for conductivity, as long as from EA001-36 for the water flow levels.

If the combination of both alerts is above a given threshold, then DSS generates an alert that there is an infiltration on the area where the sensors are located.

If DSS does not provide an alert, then the message will be a notification like below:

DSS Feed

Alert - 16/11/2022 16:37

No Infiltration Detected

Figure 2.1-22 DSS Notification

Functionality 3 - Interactive Map

HMI is providing a map with the location of the sensors, as long as polygons visualizing the monitoring area.

Figure 2.1-23 Salinity Intrusion Map - No Alerts

HMI receives the location of the sensors, as long as coordinates for every polygon, in order to visualize the monitoring area.

In the above figure, DSS has not detected any possible saline intrusion.

As a result, the map produces polygons only for the area where there is a possibility of saline intrusion, like the figure below.

Figure 2.1-24 Saline Intrusion Map - DSS Alerts

2.1.6. City Dashboard

The water consumption awareness dashboard supports water management companies & public officials to better understand available consumption data through an inclusive set of functionalities for: (i) monitoring and understanding how water is consumed in a specific area or consumption point (including schools, sport facilities, gardens, other buildings) in the course of time, leveraging the available consumption metering information from smart meters or from manual readings (e.g. Aguas de Alicante's Customer Management System includes manual readings on a monthly and quarterly basis); (ii) comparing consumption across various dimensions, including per groups of consumers, areas, types of consumption points and time periods. Stakeholders can create comparisons using filtering functionalities and become aware of the consumption across the different dimensions; (iii) take decisions regarding water consumption mitigation measures based on such information and (iv) monitor the impact of consumption mitigation measures after their implementation by comparing consumption pre- and post- interventions.

2.1.6.1. Login View

In order to access the Consumption Awareness Dashboard, users need to login using their Keyrock credentials. Keyrock is the FIWARE component responsible for Identity Management. User can login to the city dashboard through the NAIADES HMI. The login page of the NAIADES HMI is presented in Figure below.

Figure 2.1-25 Login view of the NAIADES HMI

NAIADES city dashboard redirects users to the login page of the Keyrock Identity Manager in order to sign in. The Keyrock login page is presented in Figure below.

Figure 2.1-26 Login page of the Keyrock Identity Manager

2.1.6.2. Consumption points statistics

In the main page of the dashboard (Figure below) public officials can see all the watering consumption points in a map. Figure below provides an indicative view of the related consumption points in Alicante. The consumption points are presented with different colours ranging from green to light green, yellow, orange and red, based on the level of their water consumption over the last week. The consumption points with the lowest water consumption are annotated with green colour, those with the highest consumption are annotated with red colour, while those lying in between are annotated with a gradient between green and red.

Figure 2.1-27 Main (landing) page of the Consumption Awareness Dashboard.

Figure below depicts the scale used.

Figure 2.1-28 Colour Bar used to indicate the relative level of water consumption for the various points

Users can also see the average daily water consumption for all consumption points on a graph view over the last year. In addition, the dashboard presents the yearly water consumption in cubic meters, segregated

for the different uses (schools, public gardens, municipal offices etc.) along with the respective percentages, as well as the water consumption change per consumption type over the last year. Note that percentile changes in the consumption are denoted with different colours (red/green) depending on whether they correspond to an increase or a decrease, respectively, while a steady consumption is indicated with an orange colour.

Users can also filter the depicted consumption points on the map based on their type. The consumption point types have been defined after analysing those available at the city of Alicante and include the following: public gardens, fonts, municipal offices, municipal sport facilities, schools, fire hydrants, irrigation hydrants, houses and other sport facilities. In case a filter for a specific type of consumption has been applied, both the map and the graph depicting the average daily water consumption include information for the consumption points of that type only (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-29 Indicative view of the Consumption Awareness Dashboard when the user has selected one type of consumption point. In this view the dashboard shows information for public gardens.

Users can access the water consumption details of each point by clicking on the consumption point marker in the map (displayed with a green or red colour). When the user clicks on a marker, a window pops up showing the corresponding meter id, type and weekly water consumption of the selected point (Figure below).

Figure 2.1-30 Detailed information for a consumption point can be viewed on the map by clicking the marker of the point. A popup window displays the corresponding meter id, type and weekly water consumption.

When the user clicks on the button “Show daily data” in the popup window, the chart below the map is filled in with the consumption data of the selected point as it is shown on Figure below.

Figure 2.1-31 Main page of City Dashboard showing the daily water consumption of the selected consumption point.

Public officials can also click on the “Add to chart” option to see multiple consumption points data in the same graph view and be able to compare the different consumptions. Figure below shows as an example the daily water consumption over the last year for three selected consumption points that have been “added to the chart”.

Figure 2.1-32 Main page of City Dashboard showing the daily water consumption of the three selected consumption points.

When the user clicks on the “More Details” option of the selected consumption point, the s/he is redirected to the consumption point details page as shown in Figure 12. That page provides a detailed view of the consumption at the selected point as follows. First the water consumption of the selected point during the last week compared to the previous week is shown in a sliding window format. For example, if today is Tuesday, last week’s consumption will be from the previous Tuesday to today and the previous week will be from Tuesday two weeks ago to previous Tuesday. At the top of the weekly water consumption graph, the water consumption change since last week is shown as a percentage number. The page also provides the monthly water consumption of the selected point during this year compared to the previous year. The graph that compares monthly water consumption shows water consumption of each month of the current year compared with the previous year in a sliding window format, similarly to the case of the weekly consumption. For instance, if today is the 18th of November, the graph shows water consumption comparisons from November of the previous year compared with November two years ago to October of this year compared with October of the previous year. In addition, the details page presents the yearly water consumption of the selected point and the daily, weekly, monthly and yearly water consumption change. At the top of the monthly water consumption graph, it is shown the water consumption change since last month.

Figure 2.1-33 Consumption point details page.

The user has the option to download the graphs as a pdf report by clicking the “Download” button in the consumption point details page. Figure below shows part of the water consumption report of the selected consumption point. The pdf reports can be distributed to interested stakeholders, can be printed and placed in bulletin boards, etc.

Figure 2.1-34 Indicative example of the Water Consumption Report pdf file showing the water consumption information for a selected point.

2.1.6.3. Activity Statistics

The user can navigate through the menu on the left side of the dashboard, to pages showing aggregated information for all the consumption points of each type. Note that these pages are similar to the details page of a consumption point as described above, but provide an aggregated for a selected type of points. Figure below provides an indicative view of the Public gardens page, which shows the water consumption of public gardens during the last week compared to the previous week. It also shows the monthly water consumption of public gardens during this year compared to the previous year. In addition, it presents the yearly water consumption of public gardens and the daily, weekly, monthly and yearly water consumption

change. The user can download a pdf report dedicated to the consumption points of a specific type, by clicking the “Download” button.

Figure 2.1-35 Indicative detailed view of the aggregate consumption of points of type Public Garden.

The dashboard also provides a list view, in which all consumption points of the specific type (public gardens in the example). The list can be seen by clicking the “View all” button. Figure below presents all the public gardens sorted by their water consumption in descending order. Users can search a consumption point by its name or meter ID, and see more details about each consumption point by clicking the search icon in the “More” column, which redirects to the corresponding consumption point details page.

Consumption Points	Consumption	Change	More
Meter D14FE159286I	687,790	-	Q
Meter I17BA457661R	595,242	-	Q
Meter I18BA090018Z	447,245	-	Q
Meter I17BD504857R	209,517	-	Q
Meter G16TE432986Q	206,295	-	Q
Meter I17FA405039A	169,142	-	Q
Meter I17BB050410H	85,234	-	Q
Meter D13FE056565L	82,219	-	Q
Meter G16TC427494C	81,926	-	Q
Meter I16BD085650J	75,028	-	Q

Figure 2.1-36 Indicative list view of consumption points. The view shows public gardens in Alicante.

2.1.7. Water Observatory

The Water Observatory tool provided by JSI have the following functionalities.

- **Indicators:** adding to the global indicators we are ingesting curated open datasets that have regional information about water topics of interest to the stakeholder.
- **Media:** each location has its own news and social media streams configured to priorities and aspects of the news that stakeholders define as topics of interest (e.g., floods).

- **Research:** similarly, to the media sources, the research topics allow for some customization to better fit to the needs of the local user.
- **Resources:** the natural resources information provided for exploration is geolocated to the regions of interest to the user of the platform.

2.1.7.1. Indicators View

To better understand the evolution and correlation between aspects impacting water resources, and to better observe alignment with Sustainable Development Goals, the NAIADES Water Observatory provides the user with a set of dropdown menus where the user can choose the data sources in a three-dimensional visualization. Here we consider a dynamic view over time on two axes and consider the size of balls to complete three dimensions of observation (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-37 Multidimensional animation in the analysis of global indicators

The local priorities of the NAIADES use cases are addressed in the “Local Indicator” tab changing from data ingested from global to local indicators. This view is showcasing the observation of water-related datasets linked to SDG 6 at world and country/region levels that can help us observe changes and trends (see Figure below). Both the local and global indicators can ingest new data sources that are identified of interest to, e.g., new added users bringing new priorities.

Figure 2.1-38 Higher granularity in the analysis of local indicators

To complement the analysis of indicators that can be sometimes unclear when the user wants to follow the progress of a single indicator, we have made available a single-indicator view, both to analyse global and local indicators in separate, when scrolling down from the animation, maintaining the selections. It is also possible to view the time-series deriving from the countries selected at each of these indicators in a single window for in-depth analysis (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-39 Analysis of a single indicator through time

An example of a workflow in the usage of this tab is to analyse the evolution of the water surface level, in comparison with the fresh surface water and the inland waters across 20 years in Spain, selecting the appropriate axis in the dropdown menu and changing the location from “All Countries” to “Spain”. The comparison with other countries is still visible but the behaviour for the case of Spain is highlighted. Then, to further analyse the “Alicante” case we select that case in the “Global” dropdown menu and have now available the “Local Indicators” tab. In this view, when focusing on the topic of the evolution of drinking

water conditions in the past 20 years in Spain, we can compare, e.g., the volume of drinking water, to the apparent losses of drinking water and the aid to the volume of water supplied in the public network across Spanish regions.

Navigation into the platform, step by step. Please provide every functionality that the end-user can do.

2.1.7.2. Media View

Both the traditional news media and the social media are important sources of input to the analysis of best practices in similar scenarios, and the definition of early warnings for water events. This view is exploring the information from news and social media in the context of the exploration of water-related topics that include when the weather is favourable to floods and the historical information from news and published research on these weather-related events and how to better take decisions to solve them. The water-related news is sourced in real-time using powerful text mining methods based on Wikipedia concepts to collect about 1500 news articles per day across more than 60 languages, of which a part relates to water events around the world. When selecting the Use Case in the main menu on the left, the real-time stream of news is automatically configured to search for topics that relate to the priorities and interests of the stakeholders that helped define this view, thus addressing the local interests (see Figure below).

The screenshot displays the 'WATER OBSERVATORY - ALICANTE' web interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu and a search bar. The search bar contains the query 'Water contamination' and the country is set to '-- All countries --'. There are also checkboxes for 'Reading mode' and 'Show English only'. Below the search bar is a map of Europe with a blue pin in Spain. A news article snippet is overlaid on the map, titled 'La Fundación Séneca convoca 23 contratos predoctorales de personal...' and published by 'europa press'. To the right of the map, there is a list of news articles, including the same article snippet and another one from 'Infosalus' titled 'El trasplante fecal más fibra mejora la sensibilidad a las infecciones'. At the bottom of the interface, there are logos for 'NAIADES', 'eventregistry', and 'Institut "Jožef Stefan" Ljubljana, Slovenija'.

Figure 2.1-40 Water-related news monitoring

The configuration of the news streams is done directly over the news engine API that is serving them but can be tested in the news monitoring part of the system. The user can choose water topics of interest and define priority levels, choose languages and categories, as well as define how rigorous this configuration must be, to model how much news articles the system is collecting (see Figure below).

The screenshot displays the NAIADES configuration interface, divided into several sections:

- Add conditions:** Includes input fields for 'Interests' (with a placeholder 'What are you interested in?'), 'Category' (with a dropdown 'Pick' and 'Category name' field), 'Source' (with 'Name of the news source' and 'By name' dropdown), and 'Location' (with 'Article/event location name').
- Filters:** Includes 'Article duplicates' (set to 'Hide article duplicates'), 'Content at most' (set to '30 days old'), 'Min. event coverage' (set to '0 articles'), 'Source ranking' (a slider), 'Limit to languages' (set to 'Any language'), and 'Data type' (checkboxes for 'News', 'PR', and 'Blogs').
- Topic definition:**
 - Interests:** A 'Required' checkbox is checked. Three interests are listed: 'Water pollution', 'Groundwater pollution (Groundwater contamina...', and 'Water scarcity', each with a 'Required' checkbox, a 'Suggest interests' button, and a slider between 'LOW' and 'HIGH'.
 - Categories:** A 'Required' checkbox is unchecked. One category is listed: 'dmoz:Science-->Environment', with a 'Suggest categories' button and a slider.
 - Event locations:** A 'Required' checkbox is unchecked. Three locations are listed: 'Spain', 'Romania', and 'Switzerland', each with a 'Required' checkbox, a 'Suggest interests' button, and a slider.

Below the configuration sections, there are two buttons: 'LOAD CONTENT FOR THE CURRENT TOPIC PAGE' (red) and 'SAVE CHANGES' (blue). The main content area shows a search result for '8,310 matching articles' with a 'VIEW: List' and 'SORT BY: Relevance' dropdown. Two article snippets are visible:

- Article 1:** 'Rainmaker Worldwide Inc.'s Water-Supply Deal With Carlaw Group Ltd. Will Flow To Sphere 3D; Deal To Supply Fresh Water To Africa Infrastructure...' from 'AB NEWSWIRE' on 'Thu, 15 Oct 2020, 14:22'.
- Article 2:** '《土污法》20年來已整治八成污染場址 剩餘農地預計明年底清完' from 'HINET' on 'Wed, 21 Oct 2020, 14:13'.

Figure 2.1-41 Comprehensive configuration of news sources

When the user aims to explore a certain water-related event, it can do so in the larger news engine EventRegistry. This will allow the user to further explore concepts related to the collected articles from a query, and the fundamental information that the news collection provides about the event. The user can explore the news through time and learn from what was published in the context of similar events in the region or other world regions where best practices can be derived and help planning for the future happenings (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-42 Historical news analysis at the external exploration dashboard

The system also allows the user to explore other topics that are related to the query formulated over news articles or events, to better understand how much are other topics (e.g., economy or education) associated with the water topic in analysis. At all times the subsample of news articles can be requested for further analysis (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-43 Water news categorification at the external exploration dashboard

The social media is also present through Facebook and Twitter with different data access characteristics, and applications. Through the news engine Event Registry, that we have access to in the context NAIADES supporting the research on the NWO, we are able to see the number of times that certain news is shared in Facebook and, thus, its impact in this online community.

On the other hand, we are also collecting the tweets related to certain water topics based on key-phrases in the original languages and locations of the NAIADES Use Cases. In the tab “Twitter Dashboard” we present several data visualisation modules and search boxes where the user can further configure the search to access, e.g., the average sentiment of the posts or the main topics over keywords (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-47 Identification of trends in the scientific research

Figure 2.1-48 Analysis of scientific research using an exploration dashboard

The user can also access the most recent research papers directly at this “Research” view on the “Recent papers” tab, where the details of each paper is exposed. For a further analysis, the user can access the external dashboard based on the text mining technology Searchpoint that allows to explore the literature by moving the pointer over clusters of subtopics related to the query topic and, by doing that, to reorder the articles that were queried. At the moment this is limited to the research articles in the MEDLINE open dataset that mostly relate to health topics, being relevant to explore water contamination topics.

An example of usage of this view follows that of the exploration of historical news data to access further details on a water-related event. The user can start to analyse the trends related to such event and how they evolve through time (e.g., fresh water resources), and then explore those selected trends directly in the published literature by using them as key-phrases.

2.1.7.4. Resources View

In this second version we added the dimension of natural resources to the exploration scenarios of the Water Observatory, based on ingested weather data from the ECMWF (on humidity, temperature and rainfall) and other open data sources, with a sophisticated engine to explore the states of that data and short/medium term predictions on aspects of that data. This new view will explore topics related to water in the context of the climate crisis, offering in the tab “Predictions” the long-term predictions for over 5 to 10 years on, e.g., the behaviour of a season in what regards humidity, rainfall or water levels, based on the collected historical data (see Figure below).

Figure 2.1-49 Climate change visualisation over 10 years forecast on resources availability

Moreover, it will also allow the user (through the tab “Explore”) to explore the data based on the Markov chains visual representation technology Streamstory that can show in an interactive way the distinctions between states and how they interact. This complex data visualisation model can provide additional information at each node and each transition that can help the user explore the combination of factors that explain the dynamics of, e.g., the season in regards to natural resources.

Figure 2.1-50 Exploration of water resources through complex data visualisation

An example of usage of this view starts with the selection of topics that define the focus of the study (e.g., rainfall, humidity and water level) to analyse 5- and 10-years forecasts related to these. Then, the user will continue the analysis in the tab “Explore”, interacting with the data visualisation and exploring the relations between states, clicking on states and transitions to access their characteristics, and studying their impact in the context of the problem in analysis.

3. Conclusions

By following the above navigation approach, the end-user will be enhanced with situation awareness for the leakage detection, water demand, among other functionalities. This knowledge will enable an accurate, real-time and worthy way of facing unwanted incidents, as water waste.